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3D PRINTING OF A GEOMETRY OPTIMIZED SANDWICH PANEL FOR A LUNAR ROVER'S FRAME

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May 31st, 2023

- Core's mass dispersion is homogeneous
- Could we make stiffer, lighter structures thanks to **3D printing** by redistributing the cell size ?

- Light
- High flexural modulus
- Low out of plane thermal conductivity

- For sandwich panels
 - Light
 - Stiff

2D Cellular Material Optimization

- Honeycomb-like structure
- Improve local stiffness
 - Mass distribution

• Challenge is to **smoothly distribute cells over a domain**

Classification of architected materials based on the geometry (Kladovasilakis et al.)

Optimization of sandwich panel's core

FFF of big parts with high temperature composites at high volumetric flow

Non-planar adaptive FFF with nozzle orientation control

MAXIMIZED STIFFNESS

Optimization of sandwich panel's core

FFF of big parts with high temperature composites at high volumetric flow

Non-planar adaptive FFF with nozzle orientation control

Representation of the experimental setup a) showing the punch applying a central load on the panel b) simply supported on its edges.

- Meshing with Gmsh, Solving with MSC Nastran
 - PSHELL: CQUAD8, CTRIA6
 - Bottom contact with edges
 - Imposed displacement on central nodes

Finite element model evaluation by Nastran showing the displacement field of an imposed displacement in the center of the panel.

- Cost function: Compliance
 - Amount of cells: constant
 - Mass: slightly drops
 - Stiffness: increases

Visualisation of how a voronoi diagram is generated (Wolfram)

Density

Seed distribution

Constant amount of cells (320)

15x15 grid

Cell distribution

Edge supported area

Imposed displacement

Convergence

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CONVERGENCE GRAPH

OPTIMIZATION – VARIABLES

CONVERGENCE COMPARISON

Front view of the experimental setup

Overview of the punch in the panel after failure

Load-displacement curve comparing two configurations of sandwich panels having the exact same mass

- Honeycomb limitation – core
- Optimized limitation – bottom skin

Sandwich panel views representation

Honeycomb

Optimized

Post failure specimen and failure mode identification

- Space industry can benefit from Additive Manufacturing methods to explore efficiently
- Many gaps left
 - Outgassing with porosities
 - Mechanical impact from thermal cycles
 - Degradation from radiations

MicroCT view of a high porosity raw filament of PEEK+CF

Lunar rover stress concentration and a cell distribution

- High volume, high flow and high performance 3D printing

Longboard in PLA, 800mm long

- Benefit from the 6 DOF of a robotic arm

✓ Control over fiber orientation

✓ No overhang

✓ Variable layer height

Benefits of developing non-planar adaptive slicers

First 3D printing of a rover's frame - PLA

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Le génie pour l'industrie

Actors

Funding

Supplementary Material

- Voronoi diagram generation

Generation of a Voronoi diagram
(Wolfram)

- Weighted Voronoi diagram

Generation of a Weighted Voronoi diagram
(Mu)

- Centroidal Voronoi Diagram

- Minimal energy configuration (Du): $\int_A \rho(\mathbf{x}) |\mathbf{C}_i - \mathbf{x}|^2$

- Point générateur le diagramme de Voronoi
- + Centroïde cellulaire

Iterative process of Centroidal Voronoi Diagram generation
(Moritz)

- Weighted Voronoi Stippling technique

Artistic representation of an object using dots concentration proportional to an image grayness (Secord)

- Black box
 - E.g. complex Finite Element model
 - Parametric geometry, properties, BC
 - Stiffness, max stress, etc

Black box representation (*Krauss*)

- NOMAD – Black box optimizer

"Generalized Pattern Search" (*Jacquenot*)

NURBS surface with its control points (*Greg A.L.*)

Grayscale colormap of a NURBS